

Impact of Financial Development on Unemployment: An Empirical Evidence from South Asian Countries

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Abstract

Financial development play important role in reducing unemployment from country's economy. This study examines the impact of financial development on unemployment in eight South Asian countries i.e. Pakistan, India, Bangladesh, Nepal, Srilanka, Maldives, Bhutan and Afghanistan. The panel data collected from World Bank for the period of 2004 to 2018. Three major proxies of financial development has been used as independent variables: Domestic Credit to Private Sector, Broad Money (M2), Domestic Credit Provided by Banks. For Unemployment, unemployment rate has been used as dependent variable. For control variables: FDI, Education and GDP per capita have been used. Fixed effect panel regression model has been applied. After analysis, it is found that financial development has positive impact on unemployment in South Asian Countries. However, FDI, Education and GDP per capita have negative relationship with unemployment. Therefore, this study recommends that financial development has to be increased up to the threshold level, so it can affect the unemployment in negative directions.

Keywords: Financial Development, Unemployment, South Asian Countries, Fixed effect panel data.

I. INTRODUCTION AND CONTEXT

One of the fundamental macroeconomic goals that every country wants is to reduce its unemployment. However, this goal may be difficult to achieve in developing countries. On the other hand, difficulty in reducing unemployment may be due to the structural failure of a financial sector, country's economic system, external shocks from other countries, any pandemic situation. As a result, many countries continue to struggle with the problem of generating decent jobs for their citizens. Generally, unemployment can be attributed to many factors such as policy inconsistency, increase in population, failure of academic system, wasteful public resources or funds, high cost of production, lack of foreign effective demand for local goods and services. Apart from this, little attention has been paid to how financial sector development affects unemployment. Conversely, it has been argued that the state of financial sector can also determine the course of unemployment in a country. A healthy and well-functioning financial sector is not only a harbinger of economic growth but also a source of employment generation and poverty reduction (Demirgüç-Kunt and Levine, 2009; Perez-Moreno, 2011; Jalil and Feridun 2011; Shabbir, Anwar, Hussain and Imran 2012; Aliero, Ibrahim and Shuaibu 2013).

The financial sector plays a vital role in the economic development of a country. Financial sector has noticeably enhanced through globalization process and became medium for fund transfer between savers and economic unit. Development of financial sector led to affect macroeconomic performance of economies. It provides link between saving and investment, flowing of funds from savers to investor and also facilitates the expansion of financial markets. To achieve economic development in a country there is need of more investment and production and which can only be caused by saving facility. As, such savings will then be channelized to productive resources in the form of investment.

Disruptions in the role of financial system or financial crises cause harm to economic activity like in great depression of 1929-1933, unemployment was 25% of labor force and almost 9000 banks closed their operations (Bordo, 2000) and Financial crises of 2007-2009 have started huge unemployment of 7.4% and was the chief reason for the destruction of labor market

In the light of this, this study aims to measure the impact of financial development on unemployment in South Asian Countries.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Many studies on the relationship between financial development and unemployment shows different results; some shows positive effect while a few shows negative relationship between financial development and unemployment.

Dromel et al. (2010) stated that financial development has the capacity to reduce the unemployment with a contends that increase in private credit which would lower the unemployment. Shabbir, et.al (2012) investigated relation between various indicators of financial development and unemployment and found that a credit to private sector, market capitalization and financial assets with SBP affected negatively on unemployment. It implied that unemployment rate can be boosted with help of credit to private sector which lead to increase in private investment in the economy. Aliero, et.al (2013) studies the relationship between financial development and unemployment in Nigeria for the period of 1980 to 2011 and his findings also concluded that financial development has negative impact on unemployment in Nigeria. Epstein & Shapiro, (2018) studied the relationship between financial development and unemployment volatility in advanced and emerging economies using business cycle search model with external financial structure, heterogeneity and sectorial collectral constraints. Study further suggested that that there is significant but negative link between unemployment volatility and domestic financial development in emerging and developing economies. Due to financial development, unemployment volatility is decreasing but there is quantitative relationship increasing to the extent to which input credit is prevalent in economy. So, input credit is much more important characteristics of firm structure in developing emerging economies Compared to advanced economies. Kim, et.al (2018) examined the imperfection effect of credit market on unemployment in the context of financial crises and stated that role of finance in shaping unemployment is crucial. Unemployment decreases with market orientation while increases with banking market concentration and financial development. Results also showed that unemployment depends on labor market, business and credit flexibility. Whereas, Bayar, (2016) studied the interaction among financial development, unemployment and domestic investment in 16 emerging market economies for the period of 2001 to 2014 using panel data. Unemployment rate was used as indicator for unemployment, Gross capital formation for domestic investment and domestic credit for private sector for development level of financial sector had been used for financial development. After analysis, results showed that financial development has no any significant impact on unemployment. Financial development decrease the unemployment only in Egypt, Brazil, Malaysia and Czech Republic whereas there is no any impact of financial sector on unemployment in most of the countries in their study sample.

After thorough review of literature, it was found that there is no any study available in the present body of literature which covered impact of financial development on unemployment in South Asian Countries. South Asian countries is currently the second fastest growing hub in the world and some analyst predict that growth will continue to increase up to 6 to 8% until 2030 and considering this growth in the context of broader picture of the global economy (Delinic.T, 2012; South Asia Economic Focus, 2016). This study will fill the gap and provide the policy and guidelines with empirical evidences to manage financial sector development in a better performance. Therefore, it would be advantageous and effective to analyze such important topic.

III.RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This methodology consist of quantitative analysis, where the secondary data has been collected from World Bank & IMF.

A. Sample

The sample of eight South Asian Countries namely Pakistan, India, Bangladesh, Nepal, Maldives, Afghanistan, Srilanka and Bhutan used. It includes three variables of Financial Development viz. Credit to Private Sector, Broad Money (M2) and Credit provided Banks as independent variables and for dependant variable Unemployment rate and Some control variables that have been used in literature, we added FDI, Education and GDPPC as control variable in our study used over the period 2004 to 2018.

B. Data Collection

Data of eight south Asian countries namely Pakistan, India, Bangladesh, Srilanka, Nepal, Maldives, Afghanistan and Bhutan collected from World Bank and IMF. This study covered a period of fifteen years from 2004 to 2018. Fifteen year data of 8 countries make total 120 observations which is good for panel data analysis. Our empirical approach is to examine the relationship between financial development and unemployment using panel regression analysis.

B. EMPIRICAL MODEL

An empirical model of this study is:

A linear regression model is constructed with three variables, bFDI, bFDI2 and bFDI3, representing the regression model parameters, and ϵ , the disturbance error term. The 'fixed-effects' version of the panel regression model using STATA 14.0 to examine the relationship between financial development and Unemployment rate is specified by equation:

$$umrate_{it} = \alpha_{it} + \beta FD1_{it} + Z_{it} + e_{it}$$

$$umrate_{it} = \alpha_{it} + \beta FD2_{it} + Z_{it} + e_{it}$$

$$umrate_{it} = \alpha_{it} + \beta FD3_{it} + Z_{it} + e_{it}$$

Whereas,

Umrate = unemployment rate

FD1= Credit provided by banks (proxy of financial development)

FD2= Broad money supply M2 (proxy of financial development)

FD3= Credit to the private Sector (proxy of financial development)

α_{it} = Constant

Z= control variable

e = error term

C. UNIT ROOT

Unit root test has been performed, if values are non-stationary and to avoid spurious regression results.

Table 1: Stationary Test Results (Unit Root Test)

Variables	Forms of Variables	Statistics	P-Value
Total			
Unemployment	<i>lnUnemp</i>	-1.647	0.0497
Credit By the Banks	<i>lnCred_Bban</i> <i>k</i>	-12.221	0.0000
Broad Money Credit to	<i>lnBroad_Mon</i>	-15.1071	0.0000
Private Sector	<i>lnCred_Tpriv</i>	-12.7891	0.0000
GDP	<i>lnGDP_LCU</i>	-2.9660	0.0015
Population	<i>lnPopul</i>	1.1360	0.0501
FDI	<i>lnFDI_LCU</i>	-3.3937	0.0000
GDP/C	<i>lnGDP_PC</i>	-2.7685	0.0028
Education	<i>lnEdu</i>	-31.351	0.0000

The Unit root test results shown in above table and the p value accompanied in the Unit Root test shown all the variable are stationary.

F. Hausman Test

Hausman Test applied in order to select the appropriate model i.e. Fixed effect or Random Effect Model. Random effects (RE) is preferred under the null hypothesis due to higher efficiency, while under the alternative Fixed effects (FE) is at least as consistent and thus preferred.

Hausman test results shown fixed effect is consistent across individuals while random effect vary and also if there is correlation between the variables, fixed effect is consistent. Fixed works best when you have a control variables also, it explore the relationship between predictor and outcome variables within an entity. When using fixed effect it is assumed that something within the individual may impact or bias the predictor or outcome variables and it need to control for this.

IV. RESULTS& FINDINGS

Descriptive Statistics

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of variables

Variables	N	Mean	Media n	Min.	Max.	St. Dev.
Total Unemployment	120	5.418	5.358	3.518	7.144	1.04 4
Credit By the Banks	120	10.03 1	10.167	8.158	12.14 9	1.04 1
Broad Money	120	10.29 7	10.270	8.728	12.31 7	0.99 6
Credit to private Sector	120	10.03 7	10.168	8.171	12.15 1	1.03 4
GDP	120	12.29 1	12.408	10.17 3	14.27 8	1.10 6
Population	120	7.398	7.433	5.493	9.131	1.11 5
FDI	120	10.37 8	10.422	7.811	12.47 5	1.12 6
GDP/C	120	4.893	4.899	4.004	5.821	0.36 7
Education	120	1.787	1.785	1.298	1.994	0.15 4

Table 2 representing the descriptive statistics of the variable. Total numbers of observations are 120 and balanced the panel data from the period of 2004 to 2018. The dependent variable measure unemployment rate is as follows. Mean figure of total unemployment rate is 5.418% and its standard deviation is 1.044% from its mean position. The minimum value of countries total unemployment is around 3.518% while maximum value is around 7.144%. Mean value of credit by the banks is 10.031% and its standard deviation 1.041% from its mean position. The minimum value of total unemployment is around 8.158% while maximum value is around 12.149%. Mean value of Broad Money is 10.297% and its standard deviation 0.996% from its mean position. The minimum value of total unemployment is around 8.728% while maximum value is around 12.317%. Mean value of Credit to Private Sector is 10.037% and its standard deviation 1.034% from its mean position. The minimum value of total unemployment is around 8.171% while maximum value is around 12.151%. Mean value of FDI is 10.378% and its standard deviation 1.126% from its mean position. The minimum value of total unemployment is around 7.811% while maximum value is around 12.475%. Similarly the values of mean, standard deviation, minimum & highest of each control variable are also showed in the above table.

Regression Analysis

Table 3: Regression results showing that Financial Development affect**the Unemployment in South Asian Countries (2004-18)**

Independent variables	Dependent variable: lnUnem		
	Regression 1 FE	Regression 2 FE	Regression 3 FE
Constant	17.99*** (2.036)	18.11*** (2.018)	17.99*** (2.034)
Cred_Bbank	0.081** (0.135)		
Broad_Mon		0.212*** (0.132)	
Cred_Tpriv			0.079** (0.135)
LnFDI	-0.006 (0.012)	-0.006 (0.012)	-0.006 (0.012)
LnGDPPC	-2.147*** (0.403)	-2.153*** (0.401)	-2.147*** (0.403)
LnEducation	-1.665*** (0.464)	-1.747*** (0.467)	-1.667*** (0.464)
At	Yes	Yes	Yes
Hi	No	No	No
R-Square	0.81	0.77	0.74
Hausman (FE vs RE)	26.58 (0.051)	26.86 (0.048)	26.73 (0.049)
Prob> F	4.05 (0.000)	4.07 (0.000)	4.05 (0.000)
Obs.	120	120	120

***, ** and * stand for the significance at the significance levels of 1, 5 and 10 % respectively; the bracketed value is standard error or the p value of the corresponding test statistics. if the p value of Hausman(FE vs RE) test for all regressions is larger than 0.05; the results of the stochastic effect is reported. If not, the result of fixed effect is reported

Table 3, in fixed effect regression 1 showing the result of the econometric analysis to identify the impact financial development on unemployment in South Asian countries. The number of observations in this model are 120. The result of R-square shows overall fitness of model. The R-square is 0.81 which indicates that overall model of study is acceptable. The F-test (Prob>f) standard value is <0.05. In our model Prob>f test results is 4.05 (0.000) which indicates this model is ok. This is a test F to see whether all the coefficients in the model are different than zero. Fixed effect Regression-1, showing the impact of Credit by Banks on unemployment in South Asian countries. Results shows that credit by banks has positive impact on unemployment at 1% significance level with 0.135 value of standard error. Furthermore, FDI has negative and insignificant relationship with unemployment with 0.12 value of standard error. GDP per capita is negatively significant at 1% with 0.403 value of standard error. Education has also negative impact on unemployment at 1% significance level with standard error value of 0.464.

In fixed effect regression 2, this study finds out that there is positive impact of Broad Money on unemployment in South Asian countries at 1% significance level. This finding also agree with the findings of Aleiro et al. (2013) which revealed that money supply has positive relationship with unemployment and

causing increase in unemployment in Nigeria as well as Shabir et al. (2012) study results also found that M2 minus currency in circulation to GDP ratio has positive relationship with unemployment; one percent change in currency circulation/GDP ratio caused a 2.312 percent change in unemployment rate, in the same direction.

In fixed effect regression 3, this study finds out that there is positive impact of credit to private sector on unemployment in South Asian countries at 1% significance level. This result also agrees to the study of Bayar (2016) in which he found that Cred_Tpriv has positive impact on unemployment in Hungary, Mexico. Whereas, FDI is negatively insignificant with unemployment & Education has also negative relationship with unemployment at 1% significance level. It signifies that education caused reduction in unemployment.

Lastly, the study indicated statistically significant positive relationship between financial development and unemployment in South Asian Countries.

V. CONCLUSION

The research has examined the impact of financial development on unemployment with control variable such as education, FDI and GDP per capita by employing fixed effect model regression on panel data in South Asian countries from 2004 to 2018 and from the foregoing presented and analyzed findings financial development has positive impact on unemployment.

In theories financial development is anticipated to reduce unemployment through factors of economic growth. While, a few studies and this study have reached conclusion about the relationship between financial development and unemployment. This study found financial development has positive contribution toward unemployment in South Asian countries. This contradiction can be resulted from a few potential causes. Financial development may increase unemployment through factors of economic growth such as Education, human capital, entrepreneurship and technological progress. So, this contradiction may have been augmented from imbalance between financial development and the factors of economic growth. Second, Most of the studies showed throughout the world that financial sector can be beneficial for real economy after reaching a threshold level, because financial sector usually cannot attract adequate amount of funds and as a result, do not provide and transfer funds abundantly to foster economic growth in its early stages of development. (Ogbeide et al. (2015).

Hence, underdevelopment of financial sector may be a reason of that contradiction in this study and financial development has not achieved that threshold level. More in depth studies are needed to find this contradiction in results.

Policy Maker should consider these results for revising any new plan of economic Financial Development.

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